

The Project Evaluation to Develop the Competencies, Capabilities, and Skills in Repairing Computers of People in Jompluak Local Municipality, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkram Province

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Abstract—The results of the study on the project evaluation to develop the competencies, capabilities, and skills in repairing computers of people in Jompluak Local Municipality, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkram Province showed that the overall result was good (4.33). When considering on each aspect, it was found that the highest one was on process evaluation (4.60) followed by product evaluation (4.50) and the least one was on feeding factor (3.97). When considering in details, it was found that: 1) the context aspect was high (4.23) with the highest item on the arrangement of the training situation (4.67) followed by the appropriateness of the target (4.30) and the least aspect was on the project cooperation (3.73). 2) The evaluation of average overall primary factor or feeding factor showed high value (4.23) while the highest aspect was on the capability of the trainers (4.47) followed by the suitable venue (4.33) while the least aspect was on the insufficient budget (3.47). 3) The average result of process evaluation was very high (4.60). The highest aspect was on the follow-up supervision (4.70) followed by responsibility of each project staffs (4.50) while the least aspect was on the present situation and the problems of the community (4.40). 4) The overall result of the product evaluation was very high (4.50). The highest aspect was on the diversity of the activities and the community integration (4.67) followed by project target achievement (4.63) while the least aspect was on continuation and regularity of the activities (4.33). The trainees reported high satisfaction on the project management at very high level (43.33%) while 40% reported high level and 16.67% reported moderate level. Suggestions for the project were on the additional number of the computer sets (37.78%) followed by longer training period especially on computer skills (43.48%).

Keywords—Project evaluation, competency development, the capability on computer repairing and computer skills.

I. INTRODUCTION

ACCORDING to the survey in Jompluak Local Municipality, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkram Province about the computer usage, it was found that there are 30 computer sets. However, they have not been used owing to the fact that most people in the community lack skills in computer literacy, usage, and repairing. This resulted in inefficient working process in local administration. With the problem mentioned above as well as the needs of the community people to develop their ability in computer usage,

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the researcher designed the study to develop computer literacy and computer repairing skills. This will help local people to be able to use computer in their everyday life. After the completion of the project, there was an evaluation to find the program efficiency and the ability of the local people in using computer. CIPP Model was used to evaluate the project on 4 aspects; context evaluation, input evaluation, process evaluation, and output evaluation [1]-[3].

II. OBJECTIVES

1. To evaluate the project on developing people's competency, ability, skills, and computer literacy in Jompluak Local Municipality, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkram Province.
2. To evaluate the satisfaction of people in Jompluak Local Municipality, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkram Province after joining the training.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. To Conduct This Study, the Researcher Followed the Steps Below: [4], [5].

1. Define the objectives of the study.
2. Study related literature and researches.
3. Analyze and synthesize the information from the document to develop research framework and research tool.
4. Write questionnaire for data collection of this study according to the defined behaviors.
5. Ask three experts to check face validity and IOC.
6. Select the questions with the IOC value not less than 0.5 to write the questionnaire in the field work.

There are 4 main parts in the questionnaire:

Part 1- General information of the subjects

Part 2- Evaluation of the competency, ability, skills, computer repairing skills, and computer literacy of people in Jompluak Local Municipality, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkram Province. The evaluation focused on 4 aspects: context evaluation, input evaluation, process evaluation, and output evaluation [2], [3].

Part 3- Evaluation of people's satisfaction on joining the training program. The questions are in the form of 5 rating scales; highest, high, moderate, little, and least.

Part 4- Opinion and suggestion

7. The revised questionnaire was tried-out with 20 people to find the reliability of each question.
8. Collect data with the selected subjects. Analyze the data to find mean and standard deviation.

B. Research Tool Validation [6], [7]

1. The validity of the questionnaire was investigated by 3 experts on content validity IOC value.
2. Reliability of the questionnaire was analyzed through alpha coefficient value by Cronbach. The whole reliability of the questionnaire was higher than 0.70.

Five rating scales of satisfaction with the interpretation according to Best [8] are

Range	Interpretation
4.50-5.00	highest satisfaction
3.50-4.49	high satisfaction
2.50-3.49	moderate satisfaction
1.50-2.49	little satisfaction
1.00-1.49	least satisfaction

IV. RESULTS

The results showed that most informants are male (17 persons) with the percentage of 56.47%, with the average age of 31.35 years (11 persons) at the percentage of 36.70%. Most of them are government officials (20 persons) at 66.70%.

The overall evaluation of the project showed that the highest aspect was the process evaluation (4.60) followed by the output evaluation (4.50) and the least aspect was input evaluation (3.97) with the average of 4.43.

When considering in detail, it was found that:

- 1) The context evaluation was in high level (4.23) with the highest aspect on the training atmosphere (4.67) followed by suitable procedure and target (4.30). The least aspect was on the cooperation of the project (3.73).
- 2) The overall input evaluation was rated at high level (4.23) with the highest aspect on the training technique (4.47) followed by venue and project operating office (4.33). The least aspect was on the budget of the project (3.47).
- 3) The overall process evaluation was rated at the highest level (4.60) with the highest aspect on the follow-up supervision (4.70) followed by individual staff's responsibility (4.50). The least aspect was on the problem and present situation of the community (4.40).
- 4) The overall output evaluation was rated at the highest level (4.50) with the highest aspect on the variety of learning activities and integrated benefits of the community (4.67) followed by project target achievement (4.63). The least aspect was on the continuation and regularity of the activities (4.33).

The trainees reported high satisfaction on the project management at very high level (43.33%) while 40% reported high level and 16.67% reported moderate level.

V. SUGGESTIONS

Suggestions for the project were on the additional number of the computer sets (37.78%) followed by longer training period especially on computer skills (43.48%).

A. Suggestions from This Study

1. People related to program evaluation should be the ones involving in the project so they will know how to evaluate the project properly.
2. When applying the results of the project in other contexts, there should be conducted thoroughly.
3. There should be a continuous evaluation of the project because the results can be used as a guideline to improve the project. Moreover, the cooperation of the staffs is very important for the effectiveness of the project.
4. Researcher should be aware of efficiency and effectiveness of the project by having good preparation before starting the project.
5. There should be a clear defined of the activities for everyone to follow to reduce the future problems.

B. Suggestion for Further Study

1. Context Aspect

There should be a clear description, instruction, and cooperation in conducting the project. Public relation is also important to persuade students, parents, etc to join the project.

2. Input Evaluation

Other organizations related to the community should give the support especially on the budget for the training.

3. Process Evaluation

The management team and the related people should study the problems and the needs of the community before conducting the project. After that, there should be a continuous supervision to improve a more effective operation.

4. Output Evaluation

In managing the project, the objectives of the project should support the needs of the community with various learning activities and can be integrated to the real life of the community. In addition, there should be a continuous project development for the highest and sustainable benefits of the people in the community.

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